

Estimation of 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-pyrazoline in organic solvent medium

G. B. Kulkarni^{a*}, N. T. Patel^b and M. M. Chincholkar^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, The Madhu Malancha Government Degree College, Belal-503 180, Dist. Nizamabad, India

E-mail : gbkulkarni31@rediff.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Yeshwant College, Nanded-431 602, India

^cSir C. V. Raman P.G. Educational Institute, Amravati-444 606, India

Manuscript received 19 January 2004, revised 9 September 2004, accepted 19 January 2005

Pyrazolines and their different derivatives are widely used in medicine¹⁻³. There is no suitable titrimetric method for the estimation of 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-pyrazoline (HMPDMPP) in organic solvent. Therefore in present communication, estimation of

HMPDMPP in organic solvent (acetone) by titrimetric method has been reported

Results and discussion

Enthalpimetric titration method gives best results for small concentration of HMPDMPP. In the enthalpimetric

Table 1 Titrations of HMPDMPP in acetone using alc KOH

Sl no	Wt titrated (mg)	Enthalpimetric titrations		Potentiometric titrations		Conductometric titrations	
		Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)	Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)	Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)
1	0.70	0.696	-0.60	0.697	-0.40	0.694	-0.80
2	1.40	1.408	0.60	1.403	0.20	1.406	0.40
3	2.80	2.789	-0.40	2.789	-0.40	2.808	0.30
4	5.60	5.589	-0.20	5.569	-0.55	5.628	0.50
5	8.40	8.375	-0.30	8.380	-0.23	8.411	0.13
6	11.20	11.175	-0.23	11.178	-0.20	11.236	0.33
7	14.00	13.994	-0.04	13.992	-0.06	14.034	0.24
8	16.80	16.811	0.01	16.778	-0.13	16.806	0.03
9	19.60	19.264	-1.71	19.575	-0.13	19.592	-0.04
10	22.40	22.428	0.13	22.386	-0.63	22.445	0.20
11	25.20	24.870	-1.31	25.011	-0.23	25.197	-0.01
12	28.00	27.227	-2.76	28.011	0.04	27.776	0.80
13	30.80	31.472	2.19	30.699	-0.33	30.755	-0.15
14	33.60	34.614	3.02	33.606	0.02	33.527	-0.22

Titrations of HMPDMPP in acetone using *t*-Bu₄NOH

Sl no	Wt titrated (mg)	Enthalpimetric titrations		Potentiometric titrations		Conductometric titrations	
		Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)	Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)	Wt Found (mg)	Error (%)
1	0.70	0.707	1.00	0.696	-0.60	0.707	1.00
2	1.40	1.419	1.40	1.408	0.60	1.420	1.40
3	2.80	2.722	-2.80	2.761	-1.40	2.822	0.80
4	5.60	5.622	0.40	5.541	-1.09	5.561	-0.70
5	8.40	8.422	0.27	8.524	-0.57	8.439	0.47
6	11.20	11.228	0.25	11.298	0.43	11.141	-0.53
7	14.00	14.022	0.16	13.922	-0.56	14.039	0.28
8	16.80	16.750	-0.30	16.750	-0.30	16.764	-0.22
9	19.60	19.522	-0.40	19.572	-0.14	19.550	-0.26
10	22.40	22.456	0.25	22.313	-0.39	22.294	-0.48
11	25.20	25.267	0.27	25.150	-0.20	25.151	-0.18
12	28.00	28.297	1.06	27.899	-0.36	28.034	0.12
13	30.80	31.433	2.05	30.414	-1.25	30.688	-0.36
14	33.60	32.682	-2.73	34.171	1.70	33.499	-0.30

Note

titrations curves show sudden rise in temperature at the end point. Conductometric titrations did not show sharp break but the end point could be determined by extrapolation. Potentiometric titration curves show sharp rise in potential at the end point and the percentage error is minimum. Comparison of results obtained by three different methods using both titrants have been shown in Table 1. It is observed that HMPDMPP can be estimated between 0.700 mg to 22.40 mg by enthalpimetric method, conductometric method and potentiometric method successfully with minimum errors in acetone as organic solvent using alcoholic potassium hydroxide as a titrant.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and made anhydrous using standard method⁴. HMPDMPP was synthesized by refluxing 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoyl)-2,2-dimethylene compound (0.01 M) and phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride (0.02 M) in pyridine (20 ml) for 2.5–3 h and the purity was checked by its melting point (130°C) and molecular weight (286).

A 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide (*t*-Bu₄NOH) in methanol (Thomas Baker) was diluted in required concentration using doubly distilled methanol. Alcoholic potassium hydroxide was prepared in isopropanol. Both were used as titrants. Freshly prepared titrant was always used. Titrants were standardised using standard benzoic acid in isopropanol. Stock solution containing 2.86 mg/ml of HMPDMPP in acetone and different volumes of

this solution (0.5 ml to 20 ml) were diluted to 20 ml to get different concentration of the solution.

An equiptronics digital potentiometer (Model no. 602) was used for potentiometric titrations using aluminium electrode as indicator and silver electrode as reference electrode. A digital conductometer (equiptronics) was used for conductometric titrations. Enthalpimetric titrations were carried out^{5,6} with suitable modification.

All titrations were carried out in acetone as solvent. The end point was determined from graph.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. Vani Manohar, Principal, M. M. Government Degree College, Belal for constant inspiration during this work.

References

1. W. Wilson and N. Bottiglieri, *Cancer Chemother.*, 1962, **21**, 137.
2. W. D. Ymek, B. Janik and O. Samson, *Acta Pol. Pharma.*, 1964, **21**, 211 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, **62**, 10489).
3. M. A. Metwally, M. Y. Yousif, A. M. Ismaiel and F. A. Amer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 54.
4. J. Kucharsky and L. Safarik, "Titration in Non-aqueous Solvents", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1974, 49.
5. G. D. Tembhare, M. M. Chincholkar and R. B. Kharat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 609.
6. G. D. Tembhare, M. M. Chincholkar and R. B. Kharat, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1993, **42**, 187.